

GLIAL REACTIONS IN EARLY DIABETIC RETINOPATHY AND THEIR EXPERIMENTAL CORRECTION WITH A CELLULAR PROTEIN KINASE BLOCKER**Usenko K.***Candidate of Medical Science, MD**ORCID: 0000-0001-9907-6109**Bogomolets National Medical University,**Kyiv, Shevchenko boulevard, 13, 01032*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19286125>**Abstract**

Among the mechanisms of development of diabetic retinopathy, activation of glia is of key importance, which is accompanied by the formation of specific markers: S100 protein, glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP), and vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF). The aim of the study was to establish the early mechanisms of development of diabetic retinopathy and the effect of blockade of cellular protein kinases on it. In male Wistar rats, diabetic retinopathy was modeled by a single injection of streptozotocin (50 mg/kg; Sigma-Aldrich, Co, China). Rats were divided into 3 groups: control, with insulin administration (30 U; NovoNordisk A/S, Bagsvaerd, Denmark) and with insulin and sorafenib administration (55 mg/kg; Cipla, India). Immunohistochemical study was performed. An increase in the expression of all markers was established in Müller cells and astrocytes of the nerve fiber layer, which formed muff-like plexuses around microaneurysms and newly formed capillaries along the inner surface of the retina. There was a sequence of activation of markers – first, the expression of S100 protein (astrocytic reaction) increased, then – GFAP (involvement of Müller cells and reactive gliosis), in the late period – VEGF, which caused the activation of pathological angiogenesis. Inhibition of the development of microangiopathy was established when blocking cellular protein kinases with sorafenib, which was associated with the suppression of the expression of the studied markers.

Keywords: diabetic retinopathy; microangiopathy; reactive gliosis; S100; GFAP; VEGF; sorafenib.

Introduction

The mechanisms of the initial stage of diabetic retinopathy (DR) are increased retinal vascular permeability, microaneurysm formation, exudation, hemorrhages and retinal ischemia, which causes neurosensory atrophy and leads to visual impairment [1]. The later stages are characterized by progression of hypoxia and severe retinal ischemia, nerve fiber layer infarctions, neovascular proliferation, vitreous tortuosity and hemorrhages, which leads to severe visual impairment as a result of significant vitreous hemorrhages and, in severe cases, tractional retinal detachment [2].

Among the molecular mechanisms in the early stages of DR, the key role is played by the activation of glia (reactive gliosis), which occurs directly in response to the accumulation of products of abnormal glucose metabolism with the formation of specific markers: S100 protein and glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP), as well as vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) [3]. The sources of these factors are activated Müller cells and astrocytes, which are normally quiescent and support local neuronal functions, but are significantly activated already at the early stage of DR [4]. Reactive gliosis is accompanied by significantly increased expression of VEGF and pro-inflammatory cytokines, which is the cause of increased leakage of retinal microvessels and proliferation of microvessels in ischemic areas [5]. In turn, the increase in the expression of VEGF and other factors is due to the activation of the signaling intracellular kinases Ras/Raf-1/MEK/ERK [6]. Overexpression of a protein that inhibits Raf-1 kinase prevents diabetic retinal neurodegeneration by inhibiting the p38-MAPK pathway [7]. Inhibition of MAPK3 and the p38 and NF- κ B pathways suppresses the proliferation of retinal capillary endothelial cells [8]. Therefore, inhibition of cellular protein

kinases may be a powerful measure to inhibit the development of diabetic microangiopathy at the early stages of its development.

In connection with the above, the aim of the study was to establish the early mechanisms of the development of diabetic microangiopathy and the effect of blockade of cellular protein kinases on it.

Methodology

The work was carried out in accordance with the norms and principles of Directive 2010/63/EU on the protection of animals, the Declaration of Helsinki (2008) and the requirements of the Law of Ukraine "On the Protection of Animals from Cruelty" (№1759-VI of 15.12.2009). The animals were kept in vivarium conditions on a standard diet.

The study involved 45 three-month-old male Wistar rats weighing 140-160 g. Experimental diabetes was modeled by a single intraperitoneal injection of streptozotocin (50 mg/kg; Sigma-Aldrich, Co, China). Every three days, the level of glycemia was monitored using a glucometer and disposable test strips (ACCUChek Instant, Roche, Mannheim, Germany) in blood taken from the tail vein on an empty stomach. 3 days after the injection, the blood glucose content of animals injected with streptozotocin was not less than 15 mmol/l. The animals were observed for 3 months.

After 7 days, animals with persistent hyperglycemia (n=45) were blindly randomly divided into 3 groups of 15 animals. In the 1st group (control), hyperglycemia treatment was not performed. In the 2nd group, animals were intraperitoneally injected with short-acting insulin (Actrapid HM Penfill, Novo Nordisk A/S, Bagsvaerd, Denmark) every other day at a dose of 30 U. Animals in the 3rd group were injected with insulin (according to the scheme of the 2nd group),

and also per os daily administered a solution of the protein kinase inhibitor sorafenib (200 mg, Cipla, India) at a dose of 50 mg/kg.

Animals were removed from the experiment after 7 and 28 days and after 3 months in the amount of 5 individuals in each group by lethal injection of thiopental (75 mg/kg). For morphological studies, the eyes were immersed in a 10% neutral formalin solution and embedded in paraffin. Serial histological sections 2–3 µm thick were made from paraffin blocks on a rotary microtome NM 325 (“Thermo Shandon”, England). Immunohistochemical studies were performed using monoclonal mouse antibodies against protein S100, GFAP (“ThermoFisher Scientific”, USA) and VEGF (“Invitrogen”, USA). Sections were additionally stained with hematoxylin. Microscopic studies and photoarchiving were performed using light-optical microscopes “ZEISS” (Germany) with the results processing system “Axio Imager. A2”.

Statistical analysis was performed using Statistica 10 software (StatSoft, Inc., USA). Descriptive statistics were performed by calculating means and their standard errors. Sample means were compared using analysis of variance (ANOVA), and a P value of <0.05 was considered significant.

Results and Discussion

Already on the 7th day after modeling DM, the retina of animals had quite pronounced morphological manifestations, which we presented in previous publications [9, 10]. Early manifestations of DR included a decrease in the density of nerve cells in the nuclear layers of the retina, edema of all layers, which was especially noticeable in the inner plexiform layer and the nerve layer, dilation of vessels, and areas of ischemia. In the ganglion cell layer, hypochromic neurons with pronounced vacuolation were noted, alternating with hyperchromic neurons; the density of ganglion neurons decreased. Already at this time, dilated capillaries were noted along the inner surface of the retina, usually filled with blood, sometimes with microthrombi. These changes indicated the development of neurodegeneration, which was formed against the background of metabolic and microcirculatory disorders.

According to immunohistochemical studies, an increase in the intensity of staining for S100, GFAP and VEGF was noted in the nerve fiber layer on the 7th day. S100-positive fibers and individual single cells in the nerve fiber layer corresponded to astrocytes in morphology and location, which are the first to be activated in response to the accumulation of abnormal metabolic products in the retina during hyperglycemia [5]. The macroglia marker GFAP was also detected within the nerve fiber layer at this time. The processes of Müller cells, which normally do not express GFAP, were positively stained, but under conditions of diabetes, the expression of this marker increases. VEGF-positive staining was also detected in the nerve fiber layer and corresponded to the distribution of macroglia plexuses in this layer.

Thus, early activation of the expression of markers related to the macroglia reaction and diabetic angiogenesis was established.

After 28 days, progression of the detected changes was noted. Swelling and thinning of the nuclear layers

of the retina were observed, which was especially pronounced in the outer plexiform layer. In the inner plexiform layer, edema progressed, and areas of ischemia expanded. Numerous microaneurysms were observed along the inner surface of the retina, which was consistent with clinical observations of the formation of intraretinal vascular anomalies of the retina [11].

In the inner nuclear layer, S100-positive cell bodies were well visualized, which corresponded to Müller cells in morphology, as well as interweaving macroglial fibers and individual S100-positive cells (astrocytes) in the nerve fiber and ganglion cell layers were also intensely stained. GFAP-positive staining was detected in the radial fibers of Müller cells and in the form of a border along the inner surface of the retina, where positively stained macroglial fibers formed a plexus around numerous microaneurysms. The macroglial activation observed in this study corresponds to the concept of reactive gliosis [4]. Compared with the previous term, the intensity of VEGF staining increased in the nerve fiber layer, as well as in other layers of the retina, especially in cells on the periphery of the inner nuclear layer.

After 3 months, among other manifestations of advanced DR, established signs of diabetic retinal microangiopathy were observed. Along the inner surface of the retina, densely located microvessels were observed, which had a significantly expanded lumen, often with microthrombi. In some places, vessels with several lumens were noted, enveloped by a single dense membrane, which indicated the formation of new vessels – pathological angiogenesis. Positively stained processes of macroglia were in close contact with the microvessels, which formed couplings around them. These couplings included intensely stained S100-, GFAP- and VEGF-positive fibers. If in the early stages, S100-positive elements prevailed in intensity, then in the later stages – VEGF-positive ones. That is, we could talk about a certain sequence of marker activation - the first was an increase in the expression of S100 (astrocytic reaction), then – GFAP (involvement of Müller cells and reactive gliosis) and in the late period – VEGF, which caused the activation of pathological angiogenesis of the retina.

In the group using insulin, the content of GFAP was significantly lower. This indicated a decrease in its expression, which was induced by hyperglycemia. In the group using insulin and sorafenib, the content of GFAP was the lowest, which indicated the inhibition of the overexpression of this marker and, accordingly, the suppression of reactive gliosis.

When using the inhibitor of cellular protein kinases sorafenib, the activity of morphological manifestations of DR was significantly lower. In retinal preparations, a high density of cells of the nuclear layers was preserved, edema of the plexiform layers was less pronounced, and almost no signs of microangiopathy were recorded. All the investigated markers had insignificant intensity of specific staining. In the inner layers of the retina, the S100 protein was localized only along the course of nerve fibers along the inner surface of the retina. GFAP was stained in Müller cells, but with significantly lower intensity than in the control. Weak staining, mainly of a diffuse type, was characteristic of

VEGF. Thus, it was possible to establish the suppression of reactive gliosis and the expression of the S100 protein, GFAP and VEGF under the influence of treatment.

From the classical point of view, DR is a complex of progressive changes in the microcirculatory bed, which are accompanied by ischemia, neovascularization, changes in vascular permeability and edema [12, 13]. The primary reaction of the inner retinal microcirculatory network to hyperglycemia and metabolic stress is vasodilation, which is mediated by glial autoregulatory signals. Further, progression of vascular dysfunction is observed (damage to endothelial cells, death of pericytes and thickening of the retinal capillary basement membrane) [14]. The key points are the degradation of the retinal neurovascular unit and disruption of the integrity of the blood-retinal barrier [15, 16]. The most reactive are microglia, which produce pro-inflammatory cytokines, growth factors, matrix metalloproteinases and initiate inflammation and apoptosis of ganglion neurons [12]. According to our data, the increase in S100 protein expression occurred earlier than other markers.

Our studies have supplemented the understanding of the role of macroglia activation, elements of which, undergoing reactive gliosis, contribute to the accumulation of high concentrations of growth factors around capillaries on the inner surface of the retina. It is known that the retina has wide opportunities for neovascularization due to its high metabolic demand, which can quickly get out of control under the influence of high VEGF expression [17]. The latter causes the appearance of microaneurysms and hemorrhages in the retina, apoptosis of pericytes and endothelial cells, neovascularization [18].

VEGF is the final product of activation of various cell signaling pathways, which is considered a major factor in the development of DR [19]. It enhances the processes of endothelial cell proliferation, neovascularization, increased vascular permeability, formation of collaterals, and, accordingly, the elimination of ischemia, a significant increase in VEGF expression has been noted in the vitreous and aqueous humor of patients with DR [20]. Therefore, intravitreal administration of anti-VEGF drugs is fully justified, which is the standard of therapy in the treatment of both early and severe stages of DR [21]. At the same time, there is a population of patients who do not respond to anti-VEGF therapy even despite frequent injections [22]. This fact prompts the search for new directions of influence on molecular events that unfold in DR, especially in its early preclinical stages.

These include the blockade of cellular protein kinases. It is known that the Ras/Raf-1/MEK/ERK cascade mediated the activation of VEGF expression in the retina [6], and the protein kinase inhibitor Raf-1 inhibited the development of DR by inhibiting the p38MAPK pathway [7]. Our studies have shown the prevention of the development of DR and microangiopathy when using the blocker of cellular protein kinases sorafenib. In this case, along with the absence of morphological signs of DR, the expression of S100, GFAP and VEGF proteins decreased. This indicated a

complex effect of sorafenib on various pathways for activating the expression of growth factors and markers of reactive gliosis.

Conclusions

1. A probable initiating mechanism that ensures the development of microangiopathy in DR is reactive gliosis of the retina with the activation of the expression of S100, GFAP and VEGF proteins.

2. The mechanism of inhibition of the development of microangiopathy by sorafenib can be considered its suppression of the expression of markers of reactive gliosis and pathological angiogenesis.

3. The established fact of inhibition of the development of microangiopathy in experimental DR allowed us to consider the blockade of cellular protein kinases as a promising direction of treatment, which can significantly supplement and expand the possibilities of anti-VEGF therapy, especially in the early stages of retinal damage.

The author of this study confirm that the research and publication of the results were not associated with any conflicts regarding commercial or financial relations, relations with organizations and/or individuals who may have been related to the study.

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